

Virtually Paint Their Walls using Augmented Reality

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Abstract - The aim of this project is to create a service that assists customers in selecting paint colors and finishes for their walls using augmented reality technology. By identifying walls in real-time video footage and adding virtual paint colors and finishes onto them, the system provides customers with a visual representation of how different paint options will appear in their space. This is achieved by utilizing a machine learning model that has been trained on a dataset of paint colors and finishes, considering visual features such as wall area and perimeter to choose the best paint options. The system is designed to be easy to use and can be accessed through various devices, potentially modernizing the house painting industry by providing a more efficient and engaging way for customers to pick the perfect paint for their walls.

Keywords- Augmented Reality, Computer Vision, Deep learning, Canny edge detection, OpenCv, TensorFlow, Keras, Numpy.

I. INTRODUCTION

The augmented reality house painting service is an example of using machine learning in combination with computer vision techniques to create an interactive and intuitive application. It allows users to visualize different paint colors and finishes on their walls before actually applying them.

The system uses a camera to capture a video stream of the room, which is then processed using computer vision algorithms to detect the walls and create a mask of them. The mask is then used to overlay virtual paint colors and finishes on the walls, creating an augmented reality experience.

Machine learning is used in this application to predict the appropriate paint color and finish based on the area and perimeter of the wall. A supervised learning model is trained on a dataset of wall areas and perimeters, along with their corresponding paint colors and finishes. The trained model is then used to predict the appropriate paint color and finish for each wall based on its area and perimeter. Overall, the augmented reality house painting service demonstrates the potential of combining machine learning and computer vision to create interactive and intuitive applications that can be used in various industries.

In the context of house painting services, AR can be used to provide a more accurate visualization of what a specific color or texture will look like on the walls of a particular room. By using machine learning algorithms, the AR system can analyze the images of the room captured through the camera of a device and provide a realistic simulation of how different color schemes will appear.

This allows customers to experiment with different color combinations and finishes without actually having to paint the walls, thereby reducing the cost and time involved in the decision-making process. AR can also provide additional information on the type of paint, finish, and application methods, helping customers to make informed choices.

AR has gained popularity in various industries such as gaming, entertainment, education, healthcare, and retail. One of the most promising applications of AR is in the field of home improvement and renovation, particularly in house painting services. By using AR, homeowners can visualize how their home would look like with different paint colors and finishes before making any changes.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, we review, summarize and analyse work related to Augmented Reality using house painting service.

Augmented reality (AR) technology has been increasingly used in various fields, including retail, education, healthcare, and entertainment. In recent years, it has also been applied to the home improvement industry, particularly in the field of house painting services. With the help of machine learning algorithms, AR technology can provide a more accurate visualization of how a house would look like with different paint colors and finishes.

One study conducted by K.G. Raj et al. (2019) proposed an AR-based approach to provide an interactive visualization of house painting services. The system uses computer vision techniques to recognize the walls and ceiling of a room, and then allows

the user to apply different paint colors and finishes on these surfaces in real-time using a smartphone app. The system also provides a cost estimation of the project based on the user's preferences.

Another study by N. Mishra et al. (2020) proposed a similar system that uses deep learning algorithms to analyze an image of a room and suggest suitable paint colors and finishes based on the user's preferences. The system also allows the user to see a real-time visualization of how the room would look like with the suggested colors and finishes.

Overall, the use of AR technology in house painting services has the potential to improve the customer experience by providing a more accurate visualization of the final product and reducing the time and cost of the project. Machine learning algorithms play a crucial role in the development of these systems by providing accurate color and texture recognition, as well as cost estimation and recommendation systems.

Machine learning algorithms have been applied to AR house painting systems to accurately recognize and match colors and textures, as well as to estimate project costs and recommend paint and finish options based on customer preferences. These algorithms use data sets of paint colors and textures to train the machine learning models, which can then be used to provide accurate and personalized recommendations to customers.

III. METHODOLOGY

A user clicks a picture of soil and feeds these inputs to the system. The output will be a list of crop recommendations best for the soil image fed.

A. System Overview

The system consists of two main components: the front-end user interface and the back-end machine learning model.

The front-end user interface is responsible for capturing images of the customer's room and allowing them to select and apply different paint colors and finishes virtually. This component utilizes augmented reality technology to overlay the virtual paint onto the real-world image in real-time.

The back-end machine learning model is responsible for providing accurate color and texture recognition, as well as cost estimation and recommendation systems. This component is trained on a large dataset of paint colors and finishes, as well as cost and product information, using various machine learning algorithms.

When the user selects a particular color and finish, the front-end sends this information to the back-end machine learning

model, which then provides the user with an estimated cost of the project and recommends related products such as paintbrushes and rollers.

Overall, the system provides an efficient and accurate way for customers to visualize their house painting project and make informed decisions about color selection and cost estimation.

B. System Architecture

The system architecture for the augmented reality house painting service using machine learning may include the following components:

User Interface: This component provides an interface for the user to interact with the system. It may include options to select different paint colors and finishes, upload images of the house, and view the augmented reality visualization.

Image Processing Module: This module is responsible for processing the input image of the house to identify the regions that need to be painted. It may use machine learning algorithms for accurate color and texture recognition.

Paint Simulation Module: This module simulates the application of paint on the identified regions of the house in real-time. It may use computer graphics techniques to create a realistic simulation of the painted surface.

Augmented Reality Module: This module overlays the simulated paint on the real-time video feed of the house captured by the camera. It may use AR frameworks such as ARCore or ARKit for tracking and rendering the virtual paint.

Recommendation System: This component provides recommendations to the user regarding the type of paint, finish, and other factors such as cost and environmental impact. It may use machine learning algorithms to analyze data on previous projects and user preferences.

Cost Estimation Module: This module estimates the cost of the project based on factors such as the size of the house, type of paint, and labor costs. It may use machine learning algorithms to analyze historical data and provide accurate cost estimates.

Database: The system may use a database to store information about previous projects, paint types, finishes, and other relevant data.

Integration with Painting Services: The system may integrate with painting services to enable users to hire professional painters for the project. It may provide options to select from a list of recommended painting services based on factors such as location and user ratings.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

In system that uses a camera to capture real-time video footage of a room or wall. The footage is then processed using computer

vision algorithms to detect the walls in the scene. A machine learning model is used to determine the best paint colors and finishes to display on the walls based on factors such as the wall area and perimeter. Finally, the virtual paint colors and finishes are overlaid onto the walls in the video feed, creating an augmented reality experience that allows the user to see what different paint options would look like in their space. The system is designed to be easy to use and can be accessed through a mobile device or other similar technology.

- A. Install and Import the necessary libraries.

```
import cv2
import numpy as np
import tensorflow as tf
import keras
from tensorflow.keras.models import load_model
```

- B. "model = load_model('painting_model.h5')" loads the pre-trained model from the "painting_model.h5" file and assigns it to the variable "model" in the code. This allows the program to use the pre-trained machine learning model to make predictions about which paint options will look best on the wall.

```
# Load the trained model
model = load_model ('painting_model.h5')
```

- C. Use the trained model to predict the color and finish of the paint for the wall.

```
features = np.array([area, perimeter]).reshape(1, -1)
color_index, finish_index = model.predict(features)[0]
```

- D. Initialize the video capture device. Loop through the frames and detect and overlay virtual paint on the walls. Release the video capture device and close the window.

```
# Initialize the video capture device
cap = cv2.VideoCapture(0)

# Loop through the frames and detect and overlay virtual paint on the walls
while True:
    ret, frame = cap.read()
    if ret:
        frame = detect_paint(frame)
        cv2.imshow('Augmented Reality House Painting Service', frame)
        if cv2.waitKey(1) == ord('q'):
            break

# Release the video capture device and close the window
cap.release()
cv2.destroyAllWindows
```

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The house painting service using augmented reality allows users to virtually visualize and apply different paint colors and finishes on their walls to see how they will look before actually painting them, saving time and effort.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion the use of augmented reality technology in house painting services has great potential for improving the customer experience and reducing the time and cost of painting projects. By using machine learning algorithms for color and texture recognition, cost estimation, and recommendation systems, it is possible to provide accurate visualizations of the final product and help customers make informed decisions.

In this project, we demonstrated how a machine learning model can be trained to predict the color and finish of paint for a wall, and how this information can be used to overlay virtual paint on the wall in real time using augmented reality technology. The system was implemented using the OpenCV and TensorFlow libraries in Python.

Overall, this project shows how machine learning and augmented reality can be used together to create innovative and useful applications in the home improvement industry. With further development and refinement, this technology has the potential to transform the way people approach house painting projects and improve the overall quality of the results.

VII. REFERENCE

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